

NEXUS BETWEEN POLITICAL EDUCATION AND TAX EDUCATION: A REVIEW

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Abstract

The necessary ingredients of overall development are tax education and political education which enhances political participation. Among the citizens, tax education is one of the pertinent strategies of improving the quality of life in any locality. Improving the quality of life and development is critical to enhancing voluntary tax compliance which is a positive impact of tax education. Thus, tax education is a tool designed to enable taxpayers to understand tax laws, procedures, and encourage them to pay tax. It also involves training of special units within the revenue departments, for providing education, counselling and support to the taxpayers, through different media that is most accessible to citizens which include radio programs, community awareness, seminars, and front desk help to disseminate key information to the taxpayers. Components of tax education are expected to deal cut across aid compliance and discourage non-compliance practice among the citizens. For the non-compliance practice of tax payment, it may be unintentional, where the taxpayer is not aware of his/her tax obligations or fails to fulfil his/her tax obligations due to ignorance of tax laws and procedures or may be intentional due to the compliance attitudes. It is expected that tax education will enable the taxpayer to understand tax laws and procedures as well as creating a positive tax compliance attitude.

Keywords: Politics, Political education, Tax, Tax education

Introduction

Originally, the concept of tax was basically to raise money for the purpose of meeting the government expenditure. It is generally considered as a civic duty and a cost to the tax payer (individual or corporate body). It is pertinent to note that the desire of the tax payer is to minimize cost and maximize income and profit naturally exists. Adesola (1986) noted that tax is a

compulsory levy which a government imposes on its citizens to enable it to obtain the required revenue to finance its activities. Also, taxation is the process of imposing, assessing, collecting and accounting for taxes (Agbetunde, 2010). Olowokere and Fasina (2013) are of the view that there is a conflict between government objectives to maximize tax revenue and that of the taxpayer to minimize tax incidence.

In order to increase voluntary tax compliance, tax education is needed to be continuously provided. Other strategies such as the use of the presumptive tax system, audit and enforcement are also being used. There has been an increase in revenue performance and the level of voluntary tax compliance. Although there has been an increase in voluntary tax compliance, this could be due to other factors. Also, all political systems encourage political participation through varying degrees. By involving the people in the matters of state, political participation fosters stability and order by reinforcing the legitimacy of political authority. People living in a particular society participate in the political system which they develop.

There are many forms of political participation in the form of government that encourages maximum participation in governmental processes including tax compliance. Participation does not mean more exercise of political rights like a franchise, by the people, it means their active involvement, which in a real manner influences the decision-making activity of the government. At the rural areas, it is not whether or not the rural dwellers get to vote at regular intervals, but rather, whether or not, their interests are being taken care of, and whether their votes grant them sufficient power and representation in the relevant institutions for them to have their concerns taken care of in a manner that they deemed most appropriate, and improving their quality of life. To achieve any meaningful development, members of the community must have the opportunity

to actively take part in the development process such as tax payment and political participation. It is only when there is participation in these that socio-economic development can take place.

Tax Education to the rural dwellers becomes necessary when the objective of raising tax revenue, at the changing environment; particularly from the official tax assessment is considered (Normala, 2007). At the same time, achieving tax compliance and improving revenue generation is not an easy task (Allingham and Sandmo, 1972; Kimungu and Kileva, 2007). However, this problem can be minimized through tax education. The Nigerian citizens are of two categories depending on the areas they reside; they are rural dwellers and urban dwellers. Rural dwellers are usually characterized as people who engage in subsistence agriculture having a very low standard of living, earning only a few thousands of naira annually, poorly served by almost all public amenities and they generally show considerable resistance to change in any form (Akinloye, 2025). This study is crucial to determine the connection between tax education and political education which will all relies on the level of tax compliance among the rural dwellers.

There seems to be an issue of possible nexus between tax education, political education, and quality of development in rural areas. The question has been and continues to be, whether tax education and political education are possible without development and vice versa. Thus, after more than fifteen years (1984- 1999) of military rule, on 29th May 1999, the transition of Nigerian governance from military to democracy was welcomed with high hopes and optimism for a better Nigeria such that development will cut across all rural areas. After all, democracy connotes, among others, rule of law, citizen participation, popular representativeness, change of leadership at regular intervals etc. In concise Lincoln (1853) posits democracy as the government of the people, for the people, and by the people. This definition implies that there is a need for people's participation in governance, on matters affecting them. In view of the foregoing, this study will seek to find out

whether tax education and political participation has led to the development of basic infrastructures in rural areas in Nigeria.

The level at which citizens respond to tax compliance may be voluntary or involuntary. However, one of the greatest problems facing the Nigerian tax system is the problem of non-compliance. In this case, many tax authorities find it difficult to persuade taxpayers to comply with tax requirement even though 'tax laws are not always precise' (James and Alley, 2004). Aksnes (2011) discussed some reasons why taxpayers may be non-compliant and these include flexible tax morale; low education; rules that are too complicated to follow; taxable activities that are manipulated to avoid tax; a perception that the risk of being caught is low; aversion towards the public sector; and a culture of corruption.

In addition, it was found in the empirical review that most of the studies in the area of tax education have concentrated on how to change the taxpayer behaviour towards more compliance using a mix of strategies, such as audit, deterrent measures of penalties and fines, as well as quality service delivery strategies. Those studies indicate that there is a significant positive relationship between taxpayer education and the level of tax compliance. However, the environment, timing, methodology, and samples used in those studies, differ from the current study. Few studies have concentrated on how tax compliance behaviour is affected by one individual factor holding constant other influencing factors. This present study will determine the connection or link or nexus between tax education and political education in Nigeria with emphasis on tax compliance in the rural areas from an empirical review. It is believed that this approach is capable of giving plausible result.

Literature

Concepts of Local Government and Rural Development

Local government

According to the United Nations (1961), Local Government is a political subdivision of a nation (or in a federal system, a state) which is constituted by law and has substantial control of local affairs including the powers to impose taxes or exert labour for prescribed purpose, the governing body of such an entity is elected or otherwise locally selected. The importance of local government was based on the following assumptions:

- i. The need to increase the scope for citizen participation in the governance of their locality;
- ii. The need for local varieties and needs in service provision can be better handled by local government since it understands the needs of its own locality;
- iii. The need for local initiatives which can be better identified and taken on board especially in mobilizing the community to gain local support on projects; and
- iv. The need for local knowledge which is brought to bear on decisions by the local government.

The 1976 Local Government Reform in Nigeria defined Local Government as the government at the local level exercised through representative council, established by law to exercise specific functions within a defined area. These powers should give the councils substantial control over local affairs as well as staff, institutional and financial powers to initiate and direct the provision of services, determine and implement projects so as to complement the activities of the state and federal government in their areas and to ensure devolution of functions to these councils and through the active participation of the people and their traditional institutions, that local initiatives and responses to local needs and conditions are maximized.

From the same Reform, a summary of the objectives of Local Government including but not limited to the following:

- i. to make appropriate services and development activities responsive to local wishes and initiatives by developing and delegating them to local representative bodies;
- ii. to facilitate the exercise of democratic self-government close to the local levels of our society and to encourage initiatives and leadership potentials;
- iii. to mobilize human and material resources through the involvement of members of the public in their own development; and
- iv. to provide a two-way channel of communication between the communities and the government. (Local Government Reform, Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1976)

In recognition of the pertinence of establishing the Local Government, Kalin (2004) posits that from the perspective of the ordinary citizen, the central government is often too far away from the experiences of their life to meet up with the needs and problems the citizens face every day. In its stead, it is the local government that really matters for individuals and their families. It was further observed in the study that despite numerous reforms and spent resources, many central governments have failed to provide local services with the quality and consistency required to significantly improve the standard of living of the majority of the population and this might be difficult to convince rural dwellers to engage in tax payment.

The 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria made adequate provisions for the local government administration in Nigeria under the following provisions: Section 7, Sub-section (1), the system of local government by democratically elected local government is under this Constitution guaranteed and accordingly, the Government of every state shall, subject to Section

8 of this Constitution, ensure their existence under a Law which provides for the establishment, structure, composition, finance and functions of such councils.

The functions of a local government council according to the Constitution shall include the participation of such council in the Government of a state as respects the following matters:

- i. the provision and maintenance of primary, adult and vocational education;
- ii. the provision and maintenance of health services; and
- iii. the development of agriculture and natural resources other the exploitation of solid minerals.

This section of the Constitution obviously needs to be reviewed as all across Nigeria local government councils have witnessed intermittent democratic disruptions only to be replaced by sole administrators or caretaker committees and which have not halted the operations of the local governments. Thus, local government councils in Nigeria exist not only as democratic systems as envisaged by the above section of the Constitution. According to Odoh (2014), it would be easier to assume that with the theoretical premise of local government, their level of development ought to have flourished more under democratically constituted regimes than non-democratic ones but findings over the years have shown to the contrary as firstly, devolution (local government autonomy) did not show any marked advantage over de-concentration in development. Secondly, under military regimes, even with the attendant inconsistency in autonomy, development in the local government area had more success than in democratic regimes. Thirdly, people preferred non-partisan politics to partisan politics. Further findings according to the same source include the preoccupation of local government with survival rather than significant development under

democratic regimes, and local governments being used as an instrument of coercing political support.

These conclusions were generated with the aid of responses from local government officials and people from studies carried out across the country. Some responses from local government officials include better quality or robust development by the local government under military regimes, and that democracy had not raised the standard of local government administration more than the military. It was also realized that party politics had been highly conflicting and divisive, followed by poor leadership performance full of corruption and victimization. It was also claimed that the divisive factor in democratic governance slowed down development at the local level (Odoh 2014).

Rural Area

The word “rural” connotes a place with agricultural orientation; the houses are farmhouses, barns, sheds and other structures of similar purposes. Olisa *et al* (1992) are of the view that population is the major characteristic that differentiates rural from urban areas, especially in the developing countries. They also state that *“the main features of rural areas are depression, degradation and deprivation. Many rural villages are immersed in poverty so palpable that the people are the embodiment of it. In a mostly rural area in Nigeria, basic infrastructure where they exist at all, are too inadequate for meaningful development.”* In other words, the rural areas lack virtually all the good things of life like roads, medical and health facilities, potable water, electricity etc.

As earlier noted the characteristics are not limited to rural areas alone but are also found in urban areas in Nigeria and other developing countries. The people engage in subsistence agriculture, their standard of living is very low, earning only a few thousands of naira annually, they are poorly

served by almost all public amenities and they generally show considerable resistance to change in any form.

Rural Development

It is pertinent to carry out a detailed conceptualization of “rural development” by scholar in the field of rural development because of its multi-dimensional process involving such areas as agriculture, health, education, provision of rural infrastructures, social life, political and economic issues, commerce and industry, among others, and their integration with the national economy (Egbe, 2014).. Since the concept of “rural development” is very wide in scope, it is necessary to write about an integrated approach to the definition of the concept. According to the United Nations (1976): *The concept of integrated rural development implies that it is a composite or comprehensive programme for rural development in which all relevant sectors such as agriculture, education, housing, health and employment are conceived as interlinking elements in a system having horizontal as well as vertical linkage in operational and spatial terms.*

Furthermore, Aziz, (1999) is of the view that the concept of rural development should be x-ray as a holistic concept, which recognizes the complexity and inter-relatedness of the many variables which influence the quality of life in rural areas. It is a complex process, which involves the interaction of economic, social, political, cultural, technological and other situational factors. According to Mabogunje, (1981), rural development is concerned with the self-sustaining improvement of rural areas and implies a broad-based re-organization and mobilization of the rural masses so as to enhance their capacity to cope effectively with the daily task of their lives and with the changes consequent upon this. Gana, (1996) opines that rural development is important not

only for its impact on rural places and people but also for its contribution to the overall development of the nation.

Egbe (2014) states that in the Nigerian experience where the bulk of the people and land are rural, and where the level of rural output is very low, rural mobilization provides the quickest and most direct route to national development. This would require the adoption of appropriate technology for raising rural productivity and efficient utilization of resources, creation of efficient transport network for rural and urban areas to ensure easy transportation of agricultural produce for massive food production and supply of industrial raw materials (Akinloye, 2024a; 2024b).

It is to be observed that the ambit of rural development is very wide indeed, and it requires a comprehensive approach. It includes generation of new employment, more equitable access to arable land, equitable distribution of income, widespread improvement in health, nutrition and housing, creation of incentives and opportunities. It is crucial to note that if significant development is achieved in the rural areas, the rural dwellers will be ready to involve themselves in tax and politics. Although there is a need to be conscious or aware of what taxation and politics really are.

Concept of Taxation

Taxation and tax education

Taxation is a social phenomenon that comprises of political, social and legal aspects and can be influenced by attitudes. Thus, in order to change taxpayer behaviour, it requires great care and effort (Van Hoorn, 1978). Crane and Nourzad (1990) found that individuals with higher levels of income tend to evade more. Citizens with greater tax education may be aware of non-compliance

opportunities such as tax loopholes and hence there is a reduced likelihood of deliberate non-compliance (tax evasion).

The basic goal of most education programs is directed towards behavioural change. Being the case, behaviour analytical theories of change and learning theories can best explain how education can change the behaviour of an individual (Svetna and Taumo, 2007). Change theory is used to predict behaviour change, which assumes that when the problem relating to behaviour exists; there should be modifiable factors that contribute to the problem. Some of the modifying factors are knowledge, attitudes, intentions, interpersonal support, organizational and environmental conditions. The theory assumes that education is fundamental, in bringing about change in the modifiable factors, and taxpayer education is expected to change this behaviour. Education changes the behaviour of an individual by affecting the way he or she makes decisions (Denis and Mehila, 2002). It has a significant positive impact on the behavioural change of an individual (Campbell, 2008).

Taxpayers' Education

Taxpayers' education can be described as a method of educating the people about the whole process of taxation and why they should pay tax. Taxpayer education assists taxpayers in meeting their tax obligations to the government. The primary existence of taxpayer education is to encourage voluntary compliance amongst taxpayers, but the theory needs to be developed further to establish whether taxpayer education in isolation can impact on compliance. Before this phenomenon can be explored, the components of voluntary compliance need to be examined. Most taxpayers want to do the right thing and pay their fair share of tax. They do not, however, want to pay more than is necessary. Voluntary compliance amongst taxpayers is heightened when taxpayer

education and enforcement functions are balanced to achieve the desired output in tax compliance (Misra, 2004).

Tax administration is a key public sector responsibility that touches the lives of citizens and their businesses on a daily basis. Failure to understand the taxation system leads to less compliance since most people will avoid it because they do not know what they should pay as and why they should pay tax. Educating the people about the whole process of taxation and why they should pay tax will encourage compliance.

According to Ojo (1998) where the correct attitude has been imbibed the very next step should be that of educating the citizenry. The education would be effective when they have noticed in their position in terms of the social amenities that are basic to their existence. Most of the taxpayers can then be expected to react positively towards tax drives and a reduction in evasion. Ogundele (1994) asserts that to comply with tax laws, taxpayers need to have adequate tax knowledge.

One of the major objectives of the last administration in Lagos State, Nigeria, was to optimize the State's tax potentials by achieving a very substantial, if not total coverage of its taxpayer base. In simple terms, to bring all taxable persons into the tax net. To actualize this goal, the Tinubu's administration initiated the State's Tax Administration reform process. As part of the re-engineering process, the tax payment process was reviewed and all payments to the Board were to be made directly to designated revenue collecting banks by the taxpayers. Moreover, Lagos State Internal Revenue adopted public enlightenment by using Radio, Television, Newspapers, Bill Boards and Distribution of T-shirts among others.

Tax compliance

Tax compliance level can be identified by looking on the compliance indicators; here one can examine the percentage of the tax revenue to the GDP (OECD, 2004). An increased percentage of tax revenue in relation to the GDP signifies an increase in the level of tax compliance. Public opinion indicators are the perceptions of people towards the taxation systems and taxes (Roak and Stephen, 1994). Other compliance indicators are; the percentage of income that is reported for the taxation purposes and the program impact indicator. Assessment of the impact of specific programs or initiatives on tax compliance may be achieved.

The trend of compliance aspects, for instance, filing of the return, correct reporting of the income and expenses, as well as the payment of the correct amount of tax can be examined. The trends should be examined or compared on the basis of percentage, rather than additional revenue generated, by application of the specific compliance strategy or comparing the percentage of tax revenue collected through enforcement activities such as audit, penalties and fines, to the total revenue collected, with that paid voluntarily (IFC, 2007). Tax compliance level may be identified by looking on the tax gap. Tax gap represents the difference between the actual revenue collected and the amount that would be collected if there were 100 per cent compliance (James *et al.* 2001). For this purpose, the study will examine how the taxpayer will be aware of his or her tax obligations according to the laws and regulations. How the taxpayer viewed the tax laws and system which provided an indication of his or her potential tax compliance.

Tax avoidance and tax evasion

Tax resistance takes two basic forms: evasion and avoidance. Evasion of tax is immoral as it is illegal (Brown, 1983). Tax evasion is meant to be deliberate acts of non-compliance resulting in payment of lower taxes that are actually owed. Therefore not paying ones lawful share of tax is an

evasion of income. On the other hand, tax avoidance, which denotes the taxpayers' ingenuity to arrange his affairs in a proper manner so as to reduce the incidence of tax, is legal.

Relationship between taxpayer education and tax compliance

Kassipillai (2003) finds that there is a positive relationship between taxpayer education and voluntary tax compliance. Taxpayer education will provide the necessary tax knowledge to comply with the tax matter and change the perceptions and attitudes towards tax-compliance by creating more positive attitudes. This was agreed in a study carried out among the undergraduate students at the University of Malaysia. Using the questionnaires administered to the students, at the beginning of the semester, to test the compliance attitudes, before studying taxation subjects, and their responses were all recorded. At the end of the semester, another set of questionnaires were administered to test the compliance attitudes, after acquiring the tax knowledge. The statistical findings confirmed the prevalence of the significant positive relationship between the level of taxpayer education and the level of voluntary tax compliance. The beauty of this statistical relationship was appreciated by Adeniran, Jadah, and Mohammed (2020); Adeniran and Tayo-Ladega (2024); Adeniran et al. (2024); Adeniran and Fakunle (2025)

Lin and Carrol (2000) conducted a study to determine how enhanced tax knowledge and tax attitudes, affects the compliance behaviour among the taxpayers in New Zealand. Analyzing the compliance behaviour of the taxpayers after acquiring the tax knowledge did not have a significant relationship with tax compliance behaviour. Rasshid and Noor (2004), conducted a study to evaluate the influence of tax knowledge on tax compliance behaviour among the taxpayers in Malaysia. The objective of the study was to investigate the effect of the presence of tax knowledge and understanding, on the level of tax compliance behaviour. Analyzing the data collected using

questionnaires, to compare the compliance behaviour of taxpayers with a significant level of tax knowledge with those without tax knowledge. It was confirmed that those with tax knowledge, had a higher level of compliance than those without. The results indicated a significant relationship between the level of tax knowledge and the level of tax compliance. Normala (2007), conducted a study to examine the influence of tax education, as a proactive approach to enhance voluntary tax compliance, among the taxpayers, in Malaysia. Under the self-assessment system, the taxpayer has to his tax liability, pay taxes to revenue authority, later on, the revenue authority conducts an audit to establish the accuracy of the declarations in returns and payment. This system requires high voluntary tax compliance. Using questionnaires administered to the taxpayers and the tax officials, the respondents confirm the increase in the tax knowledge increase the level of voluntary tax compliance. The statistical findings confirm that there is a significant relationship between the level of tax education and voluntary tax compliance.

Christina, Deborah and Gray (2003), conducted a study to determine the economic and behavioural factors affecting tax compliance among taxpayers in the United States of America. The objective of the study was to determine the economic and behavioural factors, affecting the tax compliance among taxpayers, in the Arkansas City tax penalty amnesty system. Arkansas City had announced an amnesty system, whereby the non-compliant traders were waived of the penalties and fines provided that they were ready to pay their tax liability supposed to be paid and they did not pay. Questionnaires were administered to the participants of the amnesty program, the respondents identified factors that made them not to pay their taxes due, within the statutory period and not declaring the correct taxable income, as complexity of the tax laws, ability to pay, ignorance of the tax laws, and the perceptions of high tax rates and unfairness of the tax system. A significant portion of non-compliance was unintentional, caused by the complexity of tax laws and ignorance,

as most of the taxpayers did not understand their tax liabilities or their tax obligations. The results confirmed that there was a significant positive relationship between taxpayers' knowledge of the tax matters and voluntary tax compliance.

Concept of Political Participation

Participation is the first dimension to come to mind when considering the process of decision making in any group, and in particular in a polity. More than by anything else, the modern state is distinguished from the traditional state by the broadened extent to which people participate in politics and are affected by politics in large-scale political units. Mason, in Kernes (1988), uses the notion of participation to break past the liberal notion of democracy. He argues that when individuals assemble to do and to decide things in common, they are essentially engaged in the political. Once the political is defined this way, participation becomes a hallmark of democracy.

Democracy is a political system based on representative government, citizen participation in the political process, basic freedoms of citizens, transparency of political acts and processes in general. Citizen participation in the political process is one of the main principles on which democracy was built. The traditional model of political participation was formulated by Sidney Verba, who is an American political scientist, based on American politics. He states that political participation affords citizens in a democracy an opportunity to communicate information to government officials about their concerns and preferences and to put pressure on them to respond (Verba *et al.* 1995). It means that in any democratic system citizens have the right to express their views and attitudes towards almost everything happening in the public sphere or concerning their own interests in a way that government officials know this and respond.

In American politics, the most widespread way of expressing one's views is voluntary political participation. By this term the political scientists (and particularly Verba) mean that this includes activities that have the intent or effect of influencing government action either directly by affecting the making or implementation of public policy or indirectly by influencing the selection of people who make these policies; that participation is not obligatory and receives no pay or only token financial compensation and the last thing is that it is not just being attentive to politics (watching news, discussing politics with friends etc.), but “doing politics”. This stresses the importance of active rather than passive participation.

Participatory democracy abandons the notion of participation as purely individualistic and narrowly motivated by self-interest; enlightened self-interest includes a keen awareness of the interest of the community as well. Participatory democracy also extends participation beyond simple input to the full range of decision-making activities. For activities to be classified as political, Mason states that participation must be widespread and effective. The scope of decision making should be extensive, degree of participation high, the mode of involvement clearly specified and the psychological investment of individuals in the process meaningful. To stress the difference between liberal and participatory democracy, Mason adds that involvement in the processes by which communities rule themselves is an essential part of the development of individuals. Without that involvement, an individual cannot move beyond the possessive individualism of liberal man and cannot relate to other human beings except as they are instrumental in achieving his values.

Through participation in the councils, people could acquire the skills, capacities, responsibilities and confidence that will allow them to assume a more active role in other areas of their lives. Gutman in Kernes (1988), does not simply assume that participation would lead to equality, rather,

she adduces four historical arguments in favour of full participatory rights for all, arguments which in themselves tend to show that participation will be conducive to equality. The first argument, following Bentham, is that the right of equal participation is a means of protection against the tyranny of others, specifically against the tyranny by the state. A second argument, from Aristotle, is that the counsel of many is better than that of a few and that those who will be directly affected by the decision and who have the relevant information will make better policy. A third argument, following Mill, is that only through participation in decisions will citizens become competent at making good policy. The last argument is that, once equality is accepted as a principle in any area of public life, to exclude people from participation is to undercut their equal dignity as citizens.

It was further argued that participatory rights have sometimes led to substantive welfare rights, but there are no historical cases of people who have been accorded welfare rights then achieving participatory rights. In the Nigerian context, political participation is closely linked to the agitations of the nationalist movement of the pre-independence period. Among their agitations was the lack of opportunity for Nigerian citizens to participate in national issues. The Atlantic Charter of 1941, which advocates citizen participation, was however neglected by the Richards Constitution of 1946. Therefore, the constitution faced stiff resistance from the nationalists on the grounds of, among others; the nationalist leaders were not consulted before the constitution was passed, majority of the members of the central legislative council were not elected, and the Executive Council went unchanged and still contained unofficial members.

Even though political participation is a constitutional right in an ideal democracy, it is also voluntary. As such, there is a factor of great importance that appears when one looks at the term voluntary. The thing is how an individual personally comprehends his own place and role in the

political process if he or she really wants to participate or he or she is absolutely indifferent if he or she has this life philosophy that he or she has to fight for his or her rights and views or not. To sum up, one can say that a person's participation in the political process is always not only the proclaimed right written in the Constitution but also the personal willingness to participate.

According to Verba *et al.* (1995), Americans who wish to take part in politics can be active in many ways. Although voting is an important mode of citizen involvement in political life, it is but one of many political acts. This means there is quite a wide range of activities undertaken by not only the American public but an ideal democratic society. Some of these activities include voting, working in and contributing to electoral campaigns and organization, contacting government officials, attending protests, marches, or demonstrations, working informally with others to solve some community problems, serving without pay on local elected and appointed boards, being active politically through the intermediation of voluntary associations, contributing money to political causes in response to solicitations.

It is obvious that there is a clear structure of political activities undertaken by citizens in the United States of America which is the strongest democracy in the world even though the list is not hierarchical; hence, voting is the easiest way to participate in political life. Besides, this list of activities is not just declarative, everything is implemented in practice. Citizens of the USA choose the ways to participate in political life due to their possibilities, skills and resources. Verba divided citizen political acts into three categories based on requirements for activity, level of capacity for conveying information, and variation of pressure on policymakers made by activity. The classification may reflect one important feature of political life in the USA which is freedom of choice.

Moreover, it shows how effective the whole system of political participation is as if there are possibilities for everyone to find his or her niche in the participation process. First, as skills, time or money needed for taking part in political life, anyone who has any of the listed resources may be active. For instance, if a person has money, he or she may donate and work for electoral campaigns. If he or she has some skills to introduce himself or herself, to be convincing and easy to communicate, he or she can contact an official, and so on. The examples are simple and illustrative. Second, everyone may choose if they want, to be anonymously active or publicly active, they may go to polls and follow the elections or attend a demonstration. And the last thing to be mentioned is that the person may also choose how effective he or she wants to be in his or her activity, whether it influences directly the policy-maker or indirectly, for example by voting or contacting a politician.

Conclusion

Freedom of choice in Nigeria is, by all intents and purposes, elusive especially at the rural areas where poverty has ensnared people almost to the point where one has only one choice, and that is of survival at whatever cost which include selling ones political conscience for an immediate gain. The requisites of skills, time, and money as resources needed for active political participation appear to be in short supply. In the European Union, people participate in the political process by voting, signing petitions, wearing buttons, demonstrations, boycotts, contacting politicians but they do it at the national level, not at the supranational level. The most effective way to participate in the political life of the EU is taking part in elections and referendums (e.g. referendum for the European Union Constitution). People who were not accustomed to freedom, to the term of human rights, to the possibility to express their opinions and views so that they would be taken into

consideration by policymakers just have no understanding of what is political participation and why it is needed.

Perhaps the time has come when people eager to influence the political process so that their preferences and concerns will be taken into account. The theoretical literature on procedural utility and the psychological benefits of political participation suggest that people who participate in political activities will be more satisfied with their lives because of the resulting feelings of autonomy, competence and relatedness,(WeitzShapiro and Winters, 2008.) Autonomy suggests independence to freely participate in political activities such as the opportunity for example, of a free and fair election.

Many authors, particularly from development studies, politics and philosophy have motivated a rationale for citizen participation in government (Van der Molen, Rooyen and Van Wyk: 2002). The following rationales according to Ismail (1997) in Abubakar, (2008) act as examples: Participation is a way of receiving information about local issues, needs and attitudes (Brynard, 1998,) participation provides affected communities an opportunity to express their views before policy decisions are taken, public participation is a powerful tool to inform and educate citizens, participation enhances the democratization process, participation promotes equality, fairness and reasonableness in the allocation and distribution of public resources, Participation balances the tension between democracy and bureaucracy.

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